

EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF MANAGEMENT OF SOVEREIGN FUNDS

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Annotation: This article discusses the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of sovereign funds. In addition, each proposed criterion examined and analyzed a set of complex indicators that assess the degree to which each criterion is met. In particular, the economic policy chosen in the activities of sovereign wealth funds is consistent with the level of use of market revenues, fiscal stability, anti-cyclical fiscal policy, ensuring the required level of asset liquidity, ensuring maximum return at the appropriate risk level, socio-economic efficiency of investment projects. evaluation indicators based on transparency criteria.

Keywords: sovereign wealth fund, stabilization fund, development fund, unit trust, world financial market, sovereign wealth funds, welfare, investment, investment portfolio, efficiency, economic efficiency, investment projects, discount rate

Today, the most important problem is implementation of an effective policy in the field state financial reserves, in particular their use for development of the national economy and industrial modernization, and balancing the main macroeconomic indicators. The formation and use of state financial reserves is subject to ensuring the balance of the main macroeconomic indicators of the state. One of the leading regimes for the formation and use of state monetary reserves is considered to be the creation of a special fund of state monetary reserves and the definition at the legislative level of the method of its formation, placement and spending. it is also confirmed for what purpose the fund of monetary reserves was formed: dynamic balance of the federal budget, stabilization of the state economy, supplying future generations with sources of profit when natural resources are depleted, etc. The developed fund of monetary reserves is considered the subject of financial and budgetary planning and forecasting, and its structure associated with the state of the state budget.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3751 of May 11, 2006, the implementation of projects on modernization and technical re-equipment of leading sectors of the economy, as well as achieving continuous, stable and balanced socio-economic development and effective structural and investment The Fund for Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, established to implement the policy, has been making a significant contribution to increasing investment in the economy and innovative development of the country.

In practice, the management of sovereign wealth funds is considered by financiers in the narrow sense as the management of the process of investing funds, ie the choice of investment instruments and investment objects, as well as changes in the requirements for investment assets.

It seems that the whole management is focused on the effective investment of funds, without focusing on the purpose of the fund.

It is important to evaluate the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds in each country.

The criterion for assessing the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds is a set of performance indicators. Criteria and indicators for assessing the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Criteria and indicators for assessing the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds [4]

	Criteria	Indicators	Evaluation features
	Correspondence of the selected economic policy to the level of use of market conjuncture revenues	Coefficient of use of market conjuncture income	The compliance of the received income with the target income is checked
	Ensuring budget stability	NBD (Non-Raw Material Budget Deficit), PNBD (Initial Non-Raw Material Budget Deficit)	The dynamics and variability of these indicators are assessed
	Pursuing fiscal policy against cycles	NBD (Non-Raw Material Budget Deficit), PNBD (Initial Non-Raw Material Budget Deficit)	The correlation of these indicators with the price of raw materials is estimated

Ensuring the required level of asset liquidity	A market spread is a time when stocks can be potentially bought	Analysis of the compliance of these indicators with the values given in the formation of the investment declaration
Ensuring maximum profitability at the appropriate risk level	Return on investment, investment risk, Sharp ratio, Trainor ratio, "observation error", "information ratio"	"Plan / reality" analysis is conducted
Socio-economic efficiency of investment projects	PP (return on investment), NPV (net income), IRR, MIRR (internal rate of return), R (return on investment), PI (profitability index), increase in the level of employment in the region, increase in wages and so on	A "plan / reality" analysis is conducted both at the design stage and during the implementation process. Based on these indicators, a decision is made on the implementation or rejection of the project
Maximum transparency of sovereign wealth activities	Linaburg-Madwell transparency index	Maximize performance

As part of the assessment of management effectiveness for all sovereign wealth funds, in our opinion, the criterion of the level of use of market conjuncture income should be applied to the selected economic policy. The level of use of market conjuncture revenues can be analyzed using the market conjuncture (raw material) income utilization coefficient, which is defined as the ratio of the use of market conjuncture income to expenditure purposes (transfers to the budget, extra-budgetary funds, etc.) to the received market

conjuncture income. Crisis situations show that the level of use should be in line with the chosen economic policy of the state.

To assess the effectiveness of the management of sovereign wealth funds, it is necessary to use the criteria of fiscal sustainability and anti-cyclical fiscal policy in order to ensure the budget system budgets or budget balance (to cover the deficit).

From an economic point of view, the budget balance is a situation in which a portion of budget expenditures quantitatively corresponds to the total amount of revenues from all sources of financing, which ensures budget stability. The budget deficit, which is not related to raw materials, is essentially a cyclical deficit, the factor of its formation is the market situation (prices for raw materials).

The main way to ensure cyclical budget balance is the formation and use of all types of budget reserves to ensure the sustainability of the expenditure side of budgets. Sovereign funds are also included in these budget reserves.

Based on the market efficiency hypothesis and modern theory of investment formation proposed by Louis Bashele [5] and further developed by Harry Markovits [6] and William Sharp [7], a number of indicators can be distinguished to assess the effectiveness of sovereign wealth portfolio management. These indicators are actively used by experts in the management of hedge funds, mutual funds and others.

A portfolio that does not have a portfolio of other investments that are able to generate greater returns at the same risk level is considered effective [8].

In our opinion, the most important criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds is to ensure maximum transparency. It should apply to all types of sovereign wealth funds. The increase in the number of sovereign wealth funds and the amount of funds accumulated in them draws serious attention to itself, as the fact that the funds of the funds can have a serious impact on the stock markets increases the transparency of activities.

The principle of transparency is the result of the joint efforts of sovereign wealth fund managers in developed economies and emerging markets to create a comprehensive framework that provides a clearer understanding of fund activities.

It is recommended to use the Linaburg-Madwell Transparency Index, developed by Carl Linaburg and Michael Madwell of the Institute of Sovereign Wealth Funds, as an understandable indicator of the level of transparency or information transparency of sovereign wealth funds.

Criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the management of individual sovereign wealth funds should be applied based on the specific type of sovereign wealth funds. The distribution of criteria for assessing the effectiveness of management by type of sovereign wealth funds is given in the table below.

Table 2

Criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the management of sovereign wealth funds by type of fund [13]

No	Funds criteria	Stabilization funds	Pension reserve funds	Unit trust	Development funds
	Conformity of the level of use of conjunctural incomes to the chosen economic pol	+	+	+	+
	Ensuring budget sustainability	+	-	-	-
	Pursuing fiscal policy against cycles	+	-	-	-
	Ensuring the required level of asset liquidity	+	+	+	+
	Ensuring maximum profitability at a given risk level	-	+	+	-
	Socio-economic efficiency of investment projects	-	-	-	+
	Ensuring maximum transparency of sovereign wealth activities	+	+	+	+

Thus, in assessing the effectiveness of stabilization funds, it is necessary to use the criteria of fiscal sustainability, anti-cyclical fiscal policy and the necessary level of liquidity of assets of sovereign wealth funds.

The criterion for ensuring the maximum return on investment at the appropriate level of risk should be applied to savings and pension funds, the main purpose of which is to ensure the maximum possible return on investment.

The criterion of socio-economic efficiency of investment projects should be used to assess the effectiveness of development funds used to finance investment projects aimed at diversification and development of the economy.

Criteria for ensuring maximum transparency of sovereign wealth funds, compliance with the level of use of business income in the selected economic policy, as well as ensuring the required level of liquidity should be used to assess the effectiveness of all sovereign wealth funds, regardless of the type of fund.

As a result of the study of the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds, the following conclusions were drawn.

First, the evaluation of the performance of sovereign wealth funds shows the extent to which fund management achieves goals and achieves planned results as a result.

Second, in assessing the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds, the level of use of conjuncture revenues in accordance with the chosen economic policy, ensuring fiscal stability, fiscal policy against cycles, ensuring the required level of liquidity of assets, ensuring maximum profitability at a given risk, socio-economic efficiency of investment projects. transparency criteria should be used.

Third, in the structure of each of the above proposed criteria, it is necessary to use complex indicators that objectively assess the level of implementation of this or that criterion.

Fourth, when applying the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds, it is advisable to use certain types of funds based on their goals and objectives.

Fifth, the criteria for ensuring maximum transparency in the activities of sovereign wealth funds, compliance with the level of use of market revenues in the selected economic policy, as well as ensuring the required level of liquidity should be used to assess the performance of all sovereign wealth funds.

Sixth, in order to ensure maximum transparency of sovereign wealth funds, it is proposed to use the Linaburg-Madwell Transparency Index for all types of sovereign wealth funds.

REFERENCES:

1. Official site Sovereign Wealth Funds Institute (SWFI) [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <http://www.swfinstitute.org/fund-rankings>.
2. On the basis of resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-3635, PQ-3636, PQ-3651 and decrees PF-5326, credit lines were opened at the expense of the Fund.
3. Suxarev O. S. Teoriya effektivnosti ekonomiki. M.: «Finansi i statistika», 2009, s. 32.

4. Vasin E.A. Povishenie effektivnosti upravleniya suverennimi fondami v Rossiyskoy Federatsii: dis. kand. ek. nauk: 08.00.10/Vasin Yevgeniy Aleksandrovich. — M., 2015. — 191 s. 36-s.

5. Bachelier, L., Theory of Speculation / L. Bachelier // Translated by D. May from Annales scientifiques de L'Ecole Normale Superieure, Ser. - 1900. <http://www.radio.goldseek.com/bachelier-thesis-theory-of-speculation-en.pdf>.

6. Markowitz, H. Portfolio Selection / H. Markowitz // Journal of Finance. - 1952. - Vol. - № 1. - P. 71—91.

7. Sharp, U.F. Investitsii / U.F. Sharp, G.Dj. Aleksander, D.V. Beyli. — M.: Infra-M, 2010. — 1028 s.

8. Stalla Review for the CFA Exams. 2007 edition. - DeVry / Becker Education Development Corp. - USA. - 2007. - P. 12—13.

9. Jumaniyozov I. et al. Impact of Development Finance Institutions on Economic Growth: Implications for Reconstruction and Development Fund of Uzbekistan //International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration. - 2018. - T. 4. - №. 2. - С. 84-88.

10. T. Jumaniyazov. (2021). The Progressive Foreign Experiments in the Activity of Sovereign Wealth Funds. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 25(2), 109–116. Retrieved from <https://www.annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/914>

11. Jumaniyazov, I. (2020) "FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF SOVEREIGN FUNDS," *International Finance and Accounting*: Vol. 2020 : Iss. 2 , Article 1. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/interfinance/vol2020/iss2/1>

12. Jumaniyozov I. ISSUES OF ENSURING THE TRANSPARENCY OF SOVEREIGN WEALTH FUNDS //International Finance and Accounting. - 2020. - T. 2020. - №. 5. - С. 1.

13. Жуманиязов Иномжон Тураевич Основные задачи Фонда реконструкции и развития Республики Узбекистан // Наука, образование и культура. 2016. №7 (10). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osnovnye-zadachi-fonda-rekonstruktsii-i-razvitiya-respubliki-uzbekistan> (дата обращения: 24.04.2022).

14. Жуманиязов Иномжон Тураевич Направления использования средств Фонда реконструкции и развития Республики Узбекистан // Economics. 2016. №7 (16). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/napravleniya-ispolzovaniya-sredstv-fonda-rekonstruktsii-i-razvitiya-respubliki-uzbekistan> (дата обращения: 24.04.2022).

15. Jumaniyozov I. Transparency Is A Key Indicator Of The Activity Of Sovereign Wealth Funds // The American Journal of Management and Economics Innovations 3 (05), 30-37

16. Jumaniyozov I. Criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of sovereign wealth funds //International Finance and Accounting. – 2021. – T. 2021. – №. 6. – C. 1.

17. Truman, Edwin M. (2008). A Blueprint for SWF Best Practices. Policy Brief 08-3 (April). Washington: Peterson Institute for International Economics.

18. Allie E. Bagnall and Edwin M. Truman. Progress on Sovereign Wealth Fund Transparency and Accountability: An Updated SWF Scoreboard // Peterson Institute for International Economics. – 2013.

